

EMERGING THE LOST CIVILIZATION OF THE MANIPUR VALLEY

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The valley of Manipur is the most densely populated area in Manipur. The valley is the administrative, educational and marketing capital of the state. The valley is populated by the Meitei community. Although rich in culture and performing arts, the origin and early history of the Meiteis are lost in obscurity. So,

the valley, surrounded by layers of mountains, is stereotypically labelled as belonging to the realm of no historical importance having no archaeological remnants of the past glory of human civilization. And some also say that the past civilization of Meitei was founded only on hand gestures and speech in the form of *meta* and abstract. But now one

cannot overlook the valley's emerging material signs of a past civilization—from gold masks to numerous ancient burial mounds. Now, a question may arise here. Why is there a lack of continuity with the past? This article will focus on a probable factor relating to mass religious conversion as well as emergence of textual record culture in the 18th century

*Aerial view of Keinou mandala,
Manipur Valley (Google Earth)*

and will also look at the discovery of another two fairly large geoglyphs in the valley in connection with the conversion theory.

T.C Hodson, who served as the Assistant Political Agent in Manipur and the Superintendent of the State and later professor of Anthropology at Cambridge, gives an able summary of Manipur and its peoples in his celebrated works, *The Meithei* (published 1908) and *The Naga Tribes of Manipur* (published 1911). He also delivered a lecture on the antiquity of Manipur entitled, "The Lesser Cathay and Its Peoples" before the China Society at the School of Oriental Studies, Finsbury Circus, (London) on Jan 12, 1922. The lecture surveyed bits and pieces of the land and culture, ranging from the country's language to religion and customs of Manipur. Since the actual transcript of the lecture is apparently not extant, the precise contents of the lecture remain unknown, but some details were recorded by the *Malaya Tribune* in its issue of 25 February 1922. This lecture was found delivered in two different titles as "Lesser Cathay and its Peoples" and "Manipur (or Lesser Cathay), an Indian Frontier State: the Country and the People." He aptly summed up the general view of Manipur as Lesser China – an Oasis of Civilization. He described the customs, history and religion of the people of Manipur, who the Burmese called *Kathe*. Here we can scarcely give an outline of his lecture, which embraced so great a variety of important and interesting subjects. The British connection was discussed from the days of the first Burmese war in 1824 to the beginning of the 20th century, when troops from the State took part in the Mesopotamian campaign and elsewhere during the war. In discussing the antiquities and superstition of Manipur, Hodson pointed to features which indicate

c. 9th century - 10th Century Dunhuang Mandala drawing, Qian Fo Dong, Gansu Province, China. (Courtesy: www.britishmuseum.org)

a Sinitic origin. The language belongs to a family of languages which includes words still current in Chinese dialects. Certain features of superstition and beliefs could be explained by a Chinese connection, which may have produced the development of an historical sense, and the material inventions of gunpowder, metal work and silk weaving, which characterize the activities of this oasis of Civilization. He presumed the date of Chinese connection is the end of the 15th

Century, approximately. The survivals of the earliest religion were illustrated, and their relation with the official religion of the State, Hinduism, was explained. One interesting subject which we need to consider here is not the Sinitic connection but the conversion of the Meithei into Hinduism. In this lecture Hodson seems to relate the conversion with big politics of Burma-Manipur relation. He said that the introduction of Hinduism in the 18th century marked the

separation, doubtless on political grounds, of Manipur from the ambit of Burmese influence. In that time Burma was an adherent Theravada man-power accumulating kingdom. The Chinese Repository, a journal published in Canton between 1832 and 1851 to inform Protestant missionary working in Asia, also gives a valuable hint as reported by the British officers who served as commanders of Gambhir Singh's Levy, on the same subject some 90 years before Hodson. In around 1780 a proclamation was made by Raja Bhagyachandra stating that, in order to avert the recurrence of calamities as then oppressed to the Meiteis by the Burmese he wholly made over his country to his celestial proprietor, Govindajee, a Hindu deity, henceforward holding the government in his name. Still today the crowning ceremony of this idol is conducted every year with the adoration of the deity with royal regalia. It seems that the political instability in Manipur due to the Burmese invasions from the 18th century up to the signing of the Treaty of Yandabo in 1826 compelled the kings of Manipur to look to Bengal for active ally in resisting against the rising Burmese, and it seems that Hinduism was adopted as one of the political strategies by abandoning the traditions and religion common with Burma, i.e., Buddhism and *nats* worship. The six- giant *mandalas* discovered in the valley of Manipur as reported in my previous article (Vol 04 Issue 01, 2018) might be the archaeological remnants of early Manipuri Buddhist tradition which could only be confirmed with certainty with further archaeological dating research and other approaches. But one thing is certain. Why only a few *Ponnas* or Meitei Brahmins who are adherent Hindus survive till today as Manipuri in Burma and how the rest of non-adherent Hindu

Gold riderless horse with parasol representing the renunciation of Siddhartha from his royal life, excavated from Manipur valley, Devi, Y.B. (ed) 2017. Temporary Exhibition on Masterpieces of Manipur State Museum Collection, Imphal: Manipur State Museum (Photo by Somorjit. W, 2016)

Cylindrical Silver casket on stand which symbolizes the prayer wheel of Buddhism, excavated from Manipur valley, Devi, Y.B. (ed) 2017. Temporary Exhibition on Masterpieces of Manipur State Museum Collection, Imphal: Manipur State Museum (Photo by Somorjit. W, 2016)

Meitei, including the royalty, were absorbed into Burmese Buddhist population is a big question? This could be a living explanation of why Manipur adopted Hinduism in the 18th century by abandoning all elements common with Burma. It is hopefully a sheer survival tactic against the all absorbing Burmese man-power accumulation policy; like the Meiteis have now started denouncing Hinduism to resist from Bengali influence since Naoria Phulo. The Burmese influence might also include Theravada expansion against other esoteric schools as recorded in the Burmese royal edicts. It is a very interesting and probably an important point and can be interpreted in myriad ways.

In order to understand more about the conversion theory, we may now turn to speculate a little on some reliable textual sources. Manipur adopted Hinduism during the reign of Charairongba (r. 1698 - 1709 CE). The conversion ceremony, which is recorded in the Court Chronicle as *Laiminglouba* meaning accepting the name of god, was held on April 9, 1709. The king also introduced construction of *kyaung* for Hindu deities. The Court Chronicle mentions the construction of *kyaungs* dedicated to two Hindu deities, Kalika and Krishna from 1706 till his death in 1709. The late 18th century text *Bhagyachandra Charita* claims that the spiritual lineage adopted by Charairongba was Nimandi (Nimbarka sect), the worship of Krishna. But the worship of Kalika, a female deity of Sakta sect, together with Krishna is vague. During the reign of Garibniwaz the entire Meitei population was mobilized for war against Burma. Besides, his reign is made infamous for his conversion atrocity. He created a Hindu political order based on *Charairongba Khunkum* (a Manipuri translation of a text by Kautilya). He

Mythical animal motif from gold jar excavated from Manipur valley similar to the Wind Horse

also employed many indirect methods like translation of Ramayana into Manipuri language to attract Hindu conversion. As mentioned by the Court translators of the Ramayana the king allowed his subjects to worship the main Meitei deity Phra Alaong in parallel with Hindu god as a soft strategy. Phra Alaong is a name given to Buddha in all the Southeast Asian kingdoms. So, he changed the name of the god into Sanamahi since 1746. He also destroyed the old statue of Phra Alaong and recast into a new one. The old metal being used again in the casting of a new statue. Thus, with this new name and new statue the old identity of the god faded away slowly and, on the other hand, Hinduism was popularized by translated versions of Hindu epics and performing art forms. Still, the reason of the conversion is highly speculative because there are no reliable evidences.

The Manipuri textual record culture is a relatively recent

phenomenon. The foundation of our knowledge of earliest Manipur is almost entirely based on unreliable secondary literary sources. Almost all the manuscripts available now in Manipur may date not earlier than the 18th or 19th century and are susceptible of proof either from paleography, or from various dating technique. But we can firmly say that the reliable text-based sources emerged in Manipur only in the 18th century. Still today we are reconstructing ancient history of Manipur based almost entirely on texts written in between late 18th and 20th century. This is a fatal flaw. We can say a crisis in our historiography. One case was the Sekta Kei. Sekta Kei was used to identify as a royal granary. But after the excavation of the site in early 1990s by ASI it reveals itself as a secondary burial site.

So the artifacts and archaeological sites unearthed from the valley by means of new scientific approaches and what we

Map of India and Manipur showing the Manipur valley and the sites of the eight Mandalas.

have been told about our history by available textual or *puya* sources are increasingly becoming more and more contradictory. There is a little hope of establishing possible links between the textual narratives and archaeological materials. We have been told that the valley of Manipur was once divided into seven clan-based principalities or kingdoms called *yeks* – Mangang, Luwang, Khuman, Angom, Kha-Ngangba, Moirang and Sarang-Leishangthem and that Manipur was created by uniting these seven clans with Pakhangba as their first king in 33 CE. The scholars who support this theory are of the view that Manipur valley was once divided into seven political boundaries of the seven principalities. But the division of the Meitei population into seven clans was probably a brain child of Garibniwaz (r. 1709-1748) in

corresponding with seven holy sages or *saptarishi*. He assigned seven *gotras* to all the Meitei populations. Why seven? Why not 10 or 34? There are 34 Scheduled Tribes in Manipur recognized by the government for administrative purposes without any religious or philosophical reason. But division of the populations of the valley into seven clans by Garibniwaz in the 18th century is somewhat religious in nature. Gotras are the progeny of the seven sages or *rishi*. The writing of *Khuman Ningthourol* (chronicle of the Khuman Clan) in the court of Ajit Shah, son of Garibniwaz, after the lineage of his queen the maid of Khuman in the mid- 18th century is a vivid example of how the chronicles of each seven principalities were written under the aegis of the Meitei court after the population was divided into seven clans and gotras. In this regard E.A

Gait is somewhat right. He opines that the ancient history of Manipur might have been compiled at a comparative recent time by the state chroniclers on no better basis than their own imagination. It will not be wrong to say that the accurate pre-18th century history of Manipur was lost in the unrecorded past. The claim of the beginning of Manipur's history from 33 CE is based entirely on the royal Chronicle *Cheitharol Kumbaba*. But the text itself says that it was copied or re-written in the court of Bhagya Chandra after the Burmese invasion in late 18th century. Besides the recording of events with exact dates starts only from 1666 CE and the records from 33 CE to 1597 CE are covered only in 28 leaves (or pages) of 12 lines each. It seems that the legends and the memories about local heroes are enumerated and reconstructed as the list of kings in a much later period. We can clearly say that till date there is no attempt to write a comprehensive history either of Manipur or of the Meiteis themselves based on rich archaeological discoveries. Even though theoretical and analytical text-based methodologies adopted by historians have become increasingly sophisticated in writing both colonial and post-colonial history, the most prestigious recent past, for instance, the exact site where the Khongjom battle was fought in 1891 is still subject to controversy.

The recent approach of aerial archaeology in Manipur with the introduction of satellite imagery in the digital public domain like Google Earth (GE), Google Earth Engine (GEE) and ISRO remote sensing digital image search engine alongside drone photography could transform the way we narrate the ancient past. The discovery of Maklang mandala and its protection and announcement as historical monument and site by the government of Manipur

in 2013 must be credited to this new approach. GEE is a cloud computing software which “combines a multi-petabyte catalog of satellite imagery and geospatial datasets with planetary-scale analysis capabilities and makes it available for scientists, researchers, and developers to detect changes, map trends, and quantify differences of the Earth’s surface.” This platform assists in archaeological remote sensing as well as archaeological site discovery through crop-marks, soil-mark, shadow marks and climatological marks. In addition to this, the advances in other branches of the arts and sciences, most notably in genetics and archaeogenetics study, contributed significantly to the growth of our knowledge of antiquity globally. For instance, in the archaic human migration theory as deduced from global mtDNA Haplogroup study, NE India is an important passageway for Homo sapiens to Southeast Asia.

Without going too far on what progress has been made since the opening of new methodologies to study our past, this article will now focus on the recent discovery of another two fairly large Mandala shaped geoglyph at Nongren and Keinou of crop mark or soil mark characters in the Manipur valley that are worthy of protection as archaeological sites as Maklang earthwork. The emerging of these clear patterns is probably due to the deficit of rain and drought like situation since 2018. The same phenomenon is reported in England in 2018 in which remnants of unrecorded pre-historic monuments and settlements have become visible during the hot summer. To understand more about this phenomenon it is worthy to mention here a bit about crop-mark and soil-mark. Crop-marks and soil-marks are technical terms used in aerial archaeology to refer to the markings

Crowning ceremony of Shri Govindajee (photograph Rajkumar Roneldrajit)

varied by color of vegetation and soil which are caused by underlying archaeological remains. Crop-mark is a crop patterns determined by the variation in growth height of crop over the forgotten human activities. The crops that grow above the buried trenches and ditch are taller and

greener due to retaining of water (*positive marks*) whereas the crops that grow over the brick structure or road or stone structure are shorter and look unhealthy due to lack of water (*negative marks*). Such feature can yield valuable result of pattern from an aerial perspective like satellite

*Aerial view of Nongren mandala,
Manipur Valley(Google Earth)*

Representative diagram of a negative cropmark above a concrete structure and a positive cropmark above a ditch

imagery especially during extreme dry season. Soil type also helps in the appearance of such feature. Compact gravel and chalk are considered as favorable for crop marks. Such marks are not visible clearly at ground level. The best season to survey such features is during a drought and heat-waves. During rainy season and wet weather these marks would gradually disappear. Soil-mark is a type of marking by which the traces of archaeology features may be visible on the surface soil as between topsoil and subsoil when disturbed by plowing in the agricultural lands. Soilmarks are visible during dry season after a good rain. There are two types of soilmarks – direct soilmarks and indirect soilmarks. By definition, soilmarks are visible when the actual archaeological sites are exposed after partial agricultural plowing of the site. Indirect soilmarks are visible when ‘the variation in the moisture-retaining or evaporation capacities of the buried feature and its surrounding matrix may give rise to variation in the colour of the ploughed soil above. A buried ditch with humic fill will retain moisture after free-draining subsoil may have dried out. Moisture will evaporate at different rates

from materials of different specific heat, producing either positive or negative dampmark’ (A dictionary of Archaeology, eds. Shaw & Jameson, p.535)

Following the recent discovery of fairly large six geoglyphs or mandalas in the valley of Manipur captured by GE imagery, another discovery of two such stains of crop-mark and indirect soil-mark characteristics in the valley of Manipur has gradually revealed Manipur valley as an intriguing archaeological hotspot and also could fill up the vacuum of its unrecorded past. Like the other six mandalas, the existence of the two sites is also entirely absent in our literary sources. Located in the paddy field in the Bisnupur District, the Keinou earthwork pattern is situated 21 km aerial distance from Kangla with the GPS coordinates of 24°40'30.4"N 93°46'52.0"E. It is similar with the Sekmai Mandala except that it has only two layers. It is a pattern of eight rayed star-shaped. It covers a total area of around 21,755.67 m² (234,176.05 ft²) with total circumference distance of 584.03 m (1,916.12

ft). Octagram shaped pattern is also locally known as *pallandabi*, a motif which is believed to be attributed the power of miraculous psychic exercises. Pallandabi is nowadays especially used in martial art ritual. It is also fascinating that both the pattern of Sekmai and Keinou are also similar with the *Khamenchatpa* motif. Although this block printed motif is very common nowadays, Khamenchatpa was worn by the nobles only after conferred upon them by the kings. It was also one of the important items of clothing restricted by the kings to be exported outside Manipur. The origin of this motif could also throw some light on our general understanding of these eight giant geoglyph or mandalas in the valley of Manipur. But its origin is also lost in obscurity. We could also compare this exclusive motif with those designed worn as mantle by high priests of various oriental monasteries in the past. The place name Keinou is well known in the history. In his book “Recent Researches in Oriental and Indological Studies: Including Meiteology”, Moirangthem Kriti Singh says that there is a peculiar Meitei Judicial Adjudication known

as Keinou Wayel. Whenever quarrels broke out between two or more individuals or groups, the matter was referred to the wise man and he gave the verdict with the help of customs and usages.

The last Mandala is discovered at a small village called Nongren in Imphal East District. It is situated 10 km aerial distance from Kangla with the GPS coordinates of 24°51'23.0"N 94°04'43.7"E along the Napet-Palli road. It is encircled by an earthwork that runs about 2.25 km (1.40 mi). It covers a total area of 268,385.90 m² 2,888,881.73 ft²). It has the archetypal protruding gates in the cardinal direction similar with those four Mandalas discovered on the bank of the Iril River. Interestingly the term Napet or Napit means those traditionally engaged in hair cutting or shaving. As early as 1998 Moirangthem Kriti Singh writes a gist about this pattern of Napet palli. He says, "Since the 15th Century it is said that some Kanaw/Shan, Napits/Barbers following Buddhism settled in the northern side of Imphal valley by order of the king and queen. A site in the north of Imphal known as Napit Palli is still to be seen."

These two sites, along with the other six sites, are worthy of further investigation and studies. With these archaeological evidences it will greatly assist to reconstruct our vacuum past. However archaeologists have yet to unearth inscription or writings associated with these remnants.

(The author wants to thank Kolom Bala and Kolom Shanthalembi for helping him to discover the two geoglyphs.)

[Plates 1

Caption:

The pattern of the mandalas discovered in the Manipur Valley is comparable with the c. 9th century - 10th Century Dunhunag Mandala drawing excavated from Qian Fo Dong (Caves of the thousand Buddhas), Gansu Province, China. (painting/mandala. www.britishmuseum.org Accessed 6 Sept. 2018)

Pattern of Khamenchatpa